

Qualification Characteristics of Participation in the Existence of Organized Group and Criminal Organization Forms

Narmanova Klara Eshnazarovna¹

¹ Ph.D. candidates, Ministry of Internal Affairs Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Abstract:

The article analyzes the opinions expressed in the scientific literature on the qualification of the act of participation in the presence of forms of organized groups and criminal associations, as well as the opinions of experts. It has been determined that there are different approaches to determining the responsibility of an organized group and a criminal association in crimes committed with participation in judicial investigation practice, and proposals aimed at eliminating them have been developed.

Also, experts' opinions on the signs and legal nature of an organized group and criminal association were studied, and suggestions and recommendations were developed regarding the definition of the scope of responsibility.

Keywords: participation in crime, organized group, criminal association, types, signs, responsibility.

It is known that the separation of participation into forms is based on the content of the roles and functional duties of several persons in the joint commission of a crime, as well as the level of their integration into one group. In turn, these signs are determined by the structure of the group, the specific characteristics of the relations of the participants of the crime within the group, the form of the agreement between them, the content of the criminal intent and the level of implementation. Therefore, the classification of crimes committed by an organized group and a criminal association is considered one of the complex issues that must be resolved within the framework of the institution of participation in crime.

Usually, besides applying the articles of the Special Part of the Criminal Code, in the qualification of the actions of the participants of the crime, in order to express the level and role of the individual's participation in the crime, it is also required to refer to the relevant part of Article 28 of the General Part of the Criminal Code.

However, this provision does not apply to the actions of the perpetrator and co-perpetrator of the crime, even if they performed the functions of organizer, witness and assistant of the crime. Because, in this case, the organizer, witness or assistants in the commission of the crime in most cases become co-perpetrators of the crime, and in this case they express the signs of the perpetrator.

The organizer, agent and assistants are considered co-perpetrators only if they fully or partially committed the acts constituting the objective part of the crime under the Special Part of the Criminal Code together with the executor. But despite this, in today's law enforcement practice, the actions of members of an organized group and a criminal association are regarded as co-perpetrators, regardless of the role they played or did not play in the commission of a specific crime, the type of participation, and their actions are considered to be co-perpetrators of the General Part of the Criminal Code. It is generally accepted that it is qualified without reference to Article 28.

In particular, such a practice was formed in the decisions of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan. For example, in paragraph 5, fourth line of the decision No. 37 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On judicial practice in cases of hijacking of vehicles" is explained that "The actions of persons who hijacked a vehicle as part of an organized group, regardless of the role of each of them, *are jointly executed* (italics is ours - N.K.) and it should be qualified with paragraph "b" of the third part of Article 267 of the Civil Code without referring to Article 28 of the Civil Code.

Also, in the third line of paragraph 12 of the decision No. 13 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court "On issues of qualification of the act when several crimes are committed", is said that "When the crimes constituting a set of crimes are committed by an organized group or criminal association, the actions of all participants of the crime, regardless of the type of participation, without applying Article 28 of the Criminal Code, it is directly qualified by the relevant article of the Special Part of the Criminal Code, which stipulates responsibility for the committed crime.

Explanations on the qualification of the actions of members of an organized group and a criminal association in this way can be found in paragraph 20, fourth line of the decision of the Plenum of the Supreme Court No. 13, in paragraph 14 of the decision No. 2 "On judicial practice in cases of violation of customs legislation and smuggling" However, in our opinion, evaluating the actions of all members of an organized group and criminal association as co-perpetrators of all crimes committed by them, equating them with perpetrators of crime, grossly violates the principle of dividing crime participants into types and does not allow to correctly assess the level and nature of their social danger.

At the same time, Akhmedova G.U rightly states that "commitment of a crime by an organized group does not solve the question of whether its participants should be considered co-perpetrators". Also, A.M. Rustambaev writes as follows on this issues: "...in crimes committed by an organized group, participants who did not commit the objective aspect of these crimes cannot be considered co-perpetrators, and the same situation is also relevant members of a criminal organization".

In addition, A.R. Kadirov proposes to introduce a separate term "quasi executor" so that the members of the organized group become executors together. In this, the author admits that "the factual role of the participants (organizer, agent, assistant) does not correspond with the legal evaluation of their activity" and considers it wrong from the point of view of legal logic. D.A. Bezborodov sees the reason for such an approach to consider the members of the organized group as co-perpetrators in order to punish the members of the organized groups with a more severe punishment. However, the scholars claims that "such practice is not fully justified, because it

violates the concept of the perpetrator of the crime to the absolute limits, does not correspond to the basic principles of criminal law, and in fact, it is possible to achieve more severe punishments for the participants of the crime by using other criminal legal instruments.

Nevertheless, such an approach to consider members of organized groups and criminal associations as co-perpetrators regardless of their role in the commission of a crime is widely supported in academic circles.

In particular, M. Kh. Rustamboev writes that "Organized group and a criminal association, the actions of participants who committed a crime in the framework of a pre-conspired group are qualified without applying Article 28 of the Criminal Code, because they are all recognized as joint perpetrators"

A. Otajanov stated that "it is not required to refer to Article 28 of the Criminal Code when qualifying crimes committed by an organized group and a criminal association, as well as by an executor. This view is also supported by M. Usmonaliev, I.A. Sottiev, M.A. Musaeu.

In addition, some authors accept this situation as an axiom. For example, P.S. in his several works says "if a person joins an organized group, it will not be necessary to determine the type of other participants and refer to the norm of the Criminal Code defining the type of participants of the crime" At the same time, N. Bugaevskaya, A. The Golovins believe that "... due to the high level of social danger of an organized group, those who participated in should be recognized as co-perpetrators"

As we can see, the main essence of the mentioned and similar views is that the actions of the perpetrator of the crime are associated with a higher level of social risk than other participants, and regardless of the role played by the members of the organized group in the commission of the crime, they are equal to the perpetrator.

But such claims are not supported by all researchers. For example, S.S. Mukhamadjonov notes the highest level of participation of the organizer in achieving the criminal result.

Ismailov notes that the degree of danger of the perpetrator and the organizer in participating in the crime is equal. However, in our opinion, not all the participants of the crime have the same level of social danger, and therefore, in any case, it is necessary to refer to the norm representing the types of participation of the Criminal Code the participants who did not take part in the full or partial performance of the objective aspect of the crime together with the perpetrator, in order to clearly define the role in the commission of the crime and to individualize the determined punishment. At the same time, equating organizers, agents and assistants to the content of the executor specified in part 2 of Article 28 of the Criminal Code cannot be a basis for considering them as executors.

However, the analysis of criminal case materials studied in terms of comparing the amount of punishment in sentencing the participants in the crime, usually indicates that the perpetrator of the crime will be punished more severely.

Therefore, the proponents of the idea that the actions of members of an organized group and a criminal association should be qualified as co-perpetrators also show that an organized group and a criminal association have their own characteristics to justify their views.

That is, in their opinion, the recognition of all members of an organized group and a criminal association as co-performers, the internal formation of these groups is related to the clear division of tasks based on the principle of specialization, and it speaks of the direct participation of these individuals in the preparation and commission of the crime.

In other words, a specific mechanism that ensures the successful implementation of the intended criminal intent in an organized group and criminal association is systematized among all its members in a certain order.

Undoubtedly, this approach to the evaluation of the joint actions of members of an organized group and a criminal association cannot be called completely unreasonable, and in most cases it is true. But it doesn't concern for all situations. For example, if we take the example of an organized group specialized in committing the crime of vehicle hijacking, one participant identifies vehicles to be hijacked, conducts observations to choose a favorable time to hijack it, and another takes measures to open the vehicle and start its engine and drives him away, the other one provides security, distributes the proceeds of crime, and so on. However, other crimes might be committed without prior planning by such a criminal group. For example, members of this group secretly rob other people's property in the process of committing a crime.

In this situation, while solving the issue of responsibility of the members of the organized group, their action is also qualified by part 4 of Article 169 of the Criminal Code. In such a situation, the sign of stability of an organized group in relation to the implementation of this crime loses its essence. In the cited case, the formation of participation corresponds to the signs of the crime committed by a group of persons. Therefore, in any cases, qualifying the act of members of an organized group and a criminal association as a joint perpetrator will unreasonably increase the social risk of the participants of the crime and lead to the imposition of a more severe punishment on them.

It should also be noted that the structure of the crime, which provides for responsibility for the crime committed by an organized group, is a special subject crime according to its formation. Therefore, in order to consider the members of an organized group as co-perpetrators in any case, it is necessary to rely on the rule that there should be subjects with such characteristics in the structure of the special subject crime.

Let's analyze this situation using certain examples. In particular, during the entire period of existence and activity of the organized group in the criminal case considered by the Chust district criminal court of Namangan region, H.G.N. financed the activities of this group.

In this, H.G.N. was not directly involved in the commission of the crime of intentional homicide. Their actions were only organizational in nature. Despite this, the actions of the H.G.N.s are included in Article 97, Part 2, Clause "p" of the Criminal Code (Intentional murder), Article 242, Part 2 (Criminal organization) of Article 28 of the Criminal Code. qualified without reference to the relevant part¹. However, logically, the assistants of the organized group in this criminal case did not directly participate in the act of taking the victim's life. From this point, what factors they could be considered as executors.

In addition, part 2 of Article 30 of the Criminal Code stipulates that "organizers and members of pre-conspired groups, criminal groups and associations shall be held accountable for all crimes they participated in the preparation or execution"(snoska). The content of the phrase "participated" in this provision, in turn, does not mean that the participation of an organizer, agent or assistant in the crime should be considered as a perpetrator, and the legislator does not directly indicate in this norm that other participants other than the perpetrator should be held accountable as co-perpetrators.

Also, in part 3 of Article 30 of the Criminal Code, it is stated that "Persons who formed or led an organized group or criminal association shall be held liable for all crimes committed by this group or association, provided that these crimes are covered by their criminal intent." . But the legislator in such situation remembers only the organizer among the types of participants. If in this case there are witnesses or assistants in the place of the organizer, what circumstances they will be held responsible for their actions as part of an organized group or criminal association.

This issue is beyond the scope of this regulation, and this regulation does not provide that the organizer should be held liable as a co-executor. Based on this, if we qualify the actions of individuals according to the provisions of the criminal law, the actions of the offenders should be qualified with reference to part 5 of Article 28 of the Criminal Code. The qualification of members

of the organized group, in this way, is more consistent with the rules formed in the practice of law enforcement and the requirements of the principles of humanity and justice.

We all know well that the current Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan does not specify one or another order of punishment based on the types and forms of the participants in the crime. In the fourth part of Article 58 of the Criminal Code, "When imposing a punishment for a crime committed with participation, the court takes into account the nature and degree of participation of each culprit in the crime. The mitigating and aggravating circumstances pertaining to the person of each participant will be taken into account by the court only when imposing punishment on this participant"

As a result, the criminal law does not distinguish between the type of crime participants and the degree, nature of their social danger when imposing punishment on perpetrators. Therefore, in our opinion, the assessment of all members of an organized group and a criminal association as acting together has no practical significance. After all, recognition of all participants as co-perpetrators, regardless of the task performed by the members of the organized group, is not based on legal norms, and at the same time, this situation also violates the principle of dividing crime participants into types.

In addition, if it is considered necessary to apply a more severe punishment to the members of the organized group and criminal association, the criminal law has enough criminal-legal means to take into account the social danger of the acts committed by them in order to impose a severe punishment.

For example, the commission of a crime by an organized group is provided as an aggravating or special aggravating feature in a number of articles of the Criminal Code as a qualifying sign of separate criminal elements. At the same time, article 56 of the Criminal Code, paragraph "m", defines the circumstances of aggravating the punishment of committing a crime by a group of persons with prior collusion or by an organized group or criminal association. In addition, in Article 242 of the Criminal Code, the establishment of a criminal association or the creation of an joined armed group, its leadership or participation in constitutes a separate crime.

From the point of view of the problem we are considering, it is important to pay attention to another aspect. Because, in any article of the Special part of the Criminal Code, the "commitment of a socially dangerous act by a criminal organization or in its interests" is not provided as an aggravating or special aggravating factor. That is why there is a reasonable question of how to qualify the crime committed by a criminal organization ordone for their interests.

Because, if the legal norm is interpreted directly, the act committed by the criminal association is considered an aggravating circumstance only according to Article 56 of the Criminal Code and constitutes an independent crime according to Article 242, Part 1 of the Criminal Code. As for the specific crimes committed by the members of the criminal association, since it is not intended as an aggravating or special aggravating feature of any crime, if there are no other aggravating circumstances in the act, their act should be qualified with the first part of this crime.

Because, the qualification of an act by a sign which is not provided for by the law with the part of the crime that implies a heavier responsibility, violates the requirements of the principles of legality and responsibility for the fault of the Criminal Code.

Unfortunately, despite this, in the case of criminal cases committed by a criminal association, the actions of its members are qualified by the norm "committed by an organized group or for its interests". For example, we can cite the following situation as an example. In particular, according to the judgment of the Yunusabad District Court on Criminal Cases dated July 3, 2013, I.'s act was qualified by Article 164, Part 4, Clause "v" and Article 242, Part 1 of the Criminal Code.

According to the judgment of the court, I. criminal partner M. on October 14, 2011, armed with black masks, rubber gloves and a baton, which he had prepared in advance to commit the crime of invasion, with the members of the criminal association, went to the yard over the entrance gate to house 6, Rakhimov 2 Berk St., Almazor District, Tashkent city. When they jumped down and attacked the owner of the house, hit him in the face and tried to tie his legs. But As long as A. actively resisting and shouting loudly, they hid from the scene without achieving their criminal goals. I. continuing his criminal activities, on the night of February 22, 2012, armed with black masks, scotch tapes and pistol-like things that he and his accomplices had previously prepared to commit the crime of invasion, 7 "A"-Oktepa berk street, Tashkent city, Yunusabad district The owner of the 7th house, Sh. and assaulted her husband F., using force, binding his limbs and mouth with scotch tape, and robbing material assets in the amount of 1,300 US dollars and 3,940,000 sums.

Taking into account the above cases, in our opinion, such cases are a violation of the requirements of the legal norm and it appears as one of the gaps in the legislation. That is why the aggravating features such as "committed by a member of an organized group or in the interests of this group", "by an organized group" and "committed by an organized group or in its interests" provided for in separate articles of the Criminal Code are referred to as "an organized group or criminal it is advisable to improve the aggravating sign "if it was committed by the association or in the interest of their interests" and "if it was committed in the interest of the organized group" in the form of "if it was committed in the interest of the organized group or criminal association".

Our research also supports this idea. In particular, the respondents were asked, "What is your attitude to the fact that in crimes committed by a criminal organization, the actions of their members or persons committed in the interests of the criminal organization are qualified by the symbol "committed by an organized group or in its interests" provided for in separate articles of the current Criminal Code?" 32 percent of the respondents said that it is correct to evaluate their actions in this manner, while 68 percent of them answered that "no, their actions are not covered by this norm." At the same time, 88 percent of those who took part in the survey believe that this norm should be improved in the form of "committed by an organized group or criminal organization or in their interests" and "committed in the interests of an organized group or criminal organization."

Based on the above, we can conclude that in order to clearly define the role of each member of an organized group and a criminal association in a specific crime, if the participants of the crime performed an organizer, witness or auxiliary function in the crimes committed as part of these associations, the actions of these individuals are the organized group of the Special Part of the Criminal Code. it is necessary to qualify the part of the article that provides responsibility for the act committed by referring to the relevant part of Article 28 of the Criminal Code. Also, in order to improve the legal basis for the crimes committed by an organized group and criminal association and the actions of its members, it is appropriate to add the following new norm to Article 30 of the Criminal Code:

In cases where the organizer, agent or assistants are members of an organized group or criminal association, they are held liable as co-perpetrators of these crimes, if they participate in the full or partial commission of the objective aspect of the crime committed by the organized group or criminal association.

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